

Energy Efficiency Performance-Tracking Platform for Benchmarking Savings and Investments in Buildings

Training material package for using EN-TRACK by Financial Institutions and Investors (final report)

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

Acronym	Description
API	Application Programming Interfaces
FI	Financial Institutions
FIF	Financial Institutions Forum
BREEAM	Building Research Establishment Environmental Assessment Method
DEEP	De-Risking Energy Efficiency Platform (DEEP)
EEl	Energy Efficiency Investment
EEM	Energy Efficiency Measure
EPBD	Energy Performance of Buildings Directive
ICP	Investor Confidence Project
LEED	Leadership in Energy and Environmental Design

1 Executive summary

This is the second of two reports that both share the objective of creating and providing training material aimed at financial institutions using the EN-TRACK platform. The focus of this second report is to provide financial institutions with a step-by-step guide to effectively access and utilise the platform outputs. Furthermore, this report serves as the foundation for the development of future material that may be developed both to guide financial institutions through the platform functionalities and outputs and also to support other further uses of the EN-TRACK platform.

The report begins with a brief introduction of the EN-TRACK platform, the target audience, and the application of the platform's outputs. A detailed platform run through then follows including an overview of the key segments and instructions on how to access the platform. Then, the main section explains how to access and retrieve the various outputs provided by the platform. This is the focal point of the deliverable. It provides a step-by-step guide to the main outputs currently available from EN-TRACK platform. It will also serve as the basis for all future platform training material that will be developed. Finally, instructions on how to download the platform outputs are provided, along with insight on the upcoming integration of the eQuad and EN-TRACK platforms.

2 Introduction

Widespread adoption of the EN-TRACK Platform as the key resource for insights on the energy, financial and other performance of buildings, relies on users having sufficient knowledge about the platform to be able to use it in an effective and meaningful way. This report and D6.3 provide complementary material for stakeholder guidance and training purposes, both focussing on financial institution D6.3 acts as a user manual and directory of the platform functionalities and outputs and acts as a reference document. In contrast, this deliverable, D6.4, focusses on providing more comprehensive, step-by-step guidance and has a training role, aiming to maximise the efficient and effective utilization of EN-TRACK platform by financial institutions. Moreover, the document may serve as a foundational resource that will underpin the development of all future training materials aimed at financial institutions. These training materials for financial institutions may encompass, but are not limited to, a user manual, video tutorials, platform wiki, communication resources, and self-paced training modules and will be continuously

created and or updated with the respect to the most recent platform iteration. The material in this report will be applied to several areas of use in the platform and various printed and online material.

The report begins with a brief introduction of the EN-TRACK platform, the target audience, and the application of the platform's outputs. A detailed platform run through then follows with an overview of the key segments and instructions on how to access the platform. This is then followed by the main section covering how to access and retrieve the various outputs provided by the platform. Instructions on how to download the platform outputs are also provided, along with insight on the upcoming platform integration between the eQuad and EN-TRACK platforms.

3 Introduction to EN-TRACK

EN-TRACK is a 'one-stop-shop' for insights on the energy, financial and other performance of buildings. EN-TRACK builds on the extensive work done under the auspices of the Energy Efficiency Financial Institutions Group (EEFIG) to create the De-Risking Energy Efficiency Platform (DEEP). The EN-TRACK platform provides access to two categories of data sets. Data on energy efficiency measures performance, and data on buildings energy performance, EN-TRACK's contribution is further accentuated through its development of comprehensive taxonomies for energy efficiency measures and building typologies, and its meticulous data collection, which collectively facilitates benchmarking activities.

Figure 1. EN-TRACK platform landing page.

3.1 User roles and hierarchy

The platform provides two levels of content for the users depending on whether or not they are registered data providers:

- **Visitor content:** This perspective caters to non-data provider users who require access to anonymized benchmarking data. Users within this view can access benchmarking data without requiring registration on the platform. Notable users within this category include financial institutions.
- **Client content:** Designed for data providers, this view grants users access to comprehensive benchmarking and monitoring services. Users in this view must be registered data providers to utilize these detailed benchmarking and monitoring services. A prime example of users within this category is building owners. Building owners can create an eQuad account and then seamlessly

transfer their buildings and projects from EN-TRACK to eQuad. They can then be processed for {"for" or "by"?} financing and investment funds, property managers and financial institutions. These can then transfer their investment performance data back to EN-TRACK

3.1.1 Visitor Content: Financial institutions

This report is tailored for entities engaged in financial and monetary transactions, including but not limited to loans, investments, and participation in financial markets. Specifically, our target audience comprises **investment funds, commercial banks, investment banks, brokerage firms, and insurance companies**. These "Financial institutions" demonstrate a strong grasp of energy conservation measures and energy savings and are actively seeking insights into the bankability of energy efficiency initiatives within specific environments.

3.1.2 Summary of application of EN-TRACK outputs for Financial Institutions

They can be combined as stand-alone outputs and, depending on any particular investment criteria and strategy, can serve to identify new opportunities and help in the decision-making process.

- Use EN-TRACK to identify low performing buildings (which represent a good investment opportunity).
- Identify costs and savings associated with your investment portfolio.
- Risk and sensitivity analysis of EEM portfolios in different settings.
- Assess and report on carbon savings.
- Identifying trends in EEM financial performance to improve investment strategies and financial forecasting.
- Looking at variations in financial performance across EEM portfolios to determine the portfolio's risk of underperformance.
- Track investments and performance in competing technologies. Understand which technology is the best for the opportunity at hand and make an informed decision.

3.2 Accessing the Outputs EN-TRACK

This section serves to guide users through the platform's key sections and help them familiarise themselves with the functionalities of each section. Financial Institutions and other non-data providers can access these functionalities without registering on the platform, enabling them to get a fast start on exploiting the platform to the full.

Figure 2. Backend process flow and navigation path of visitor content

Once on the platform, users will find options to explore Building Performance benchmarking or Energy Efficiency Measures benchmarking by clicking on either on the "Building Performance" or "Energy Efficiency Measures" on the top bar of the landing page, or by clicking the Buildings "compare" button or Energy Efficiency Measures "explore" button on the main page. This selection will determine the specific outputs they wish to review.

Annex 1 serves as a comprehensive introduction for financial institutions to the EN-TRACK platform. It not only acquaints them with the platform but also functions as a mechanism for identifying prospective enhancements and novel functionalities. These improvements aim to enhance the information services tailored to the specific needs of financial institutions engaged in Energy Efficiency projects within building environments.

3.2.1 Buildings performance benchmarking

Once in the building performance benchmarking page, financial institutions will find the graphical analysis of energy use intensity in buildings as the primary indicator. Figure 3 below provides a visual overview of the pages. Additionally, users can compare energy cost intensity and energy emission intensity by clicking on cost and emission on the capsule shaped bar on the top right of the page. These insights provide valuable additional reference points when assessing projects in buildings and assist in the estimation of a proposed project's potential to deliver the desired outcomes.

Figure 3. Financial institution view: Buildings performance benchmarking landing page

Users have the flexibility to tailor their data viewing experience based on their preferences. Users can switch between two modes, by selecting from a drop down list in the view mode: table view and graphical view, specifically, the boxplot diagram. **Boxplot Diagrams:** Boxplot diagrams offer a visual representation of numerical data by displaying the quartiles of the dataset, dividing the data range into four equal parts of 25%. These diagrams present the following key statistics: minimum score, first quartile, median, third quartile, and maximum score.

Figure 4. Financial institution view: Buildings performance benchmarking table view mode

Table View: In table mode as seen in figure 4, the data is presented in a structured format. Users can see a list of building types featured in the dataset, along with the mean of the indicator they are viewing and the number of buildings per building type.

Filtering Options: To further refine your data exploration, you can utilize the filter function located on the left side of the page. You have the option to filter data based on country, time period, area size (measured in square meters), and energy consumption data, which can be either real or normative consumption. This empowers you to customize your analysis according to your specific criteria and requirements.

3.2.2 Energy efficiency measures

The main landing page of the energy efficiency measures benchmarking displays the graphical analysis of energy use savings intensity as the primary indicator. The figure 5 below provides a visual overview of the pages. Additionally, on the capsule shaped bar at the top right of the page users can click on and compare the following:

- **Financial savings:** energy cost savings intensity
- **Emission savings:** energy emission savings intensity,
- **Cost:** Normalised Investment Cost, Avoidance Cost By Clicking On Cost,
- **Finance:** Internal Rate of Return, Net Present Value, Net Present Value Quotient, Simple Payback, Profitability Index

Using these insights provides additional reference when assessing application of energy efficiency measures in buildings, to assist in the estimation of a proposed EEMs potential to deliver the desired results.

Figure 5. Financial institution view: EEM benchmarking landing page

As with the building performance benchmarking page, users can tailor their data viewing options as graphics or as tables by selecting the view mode at the top right of the indicator display section.

Figure 6. Financial institution view: EEM benchmarking landing page table view mode

4 Sourcing outputs

This section provides instructions for accessing the diverse range of financial and energy performance indicators for buildings and EEMs provided by EN-TRACK. The performance monitoring and benchmarking of buildings cover three aspects: energy consumption, energy cost, and energy consumption related CO₂ emissions. These are represented by three indicators: Energy Use Intensity (EUI) [kWh/m².yr], Energy Cost Intensity (ECI) [€/m².yr], and Carbon Emission Intensity (CEI) [kgCO₂/m².yr].

The performance monitoring and benchmarking of EEM covers four aspects: energy saving, cost saving, CO₂ emissions saving, and investments. In overall, 10 different indicators are used for this: Energy Use Saving Intensity (EUSI) [kWh/m².yr], Energy Cost Saving Intensity (ECSI) [€/m².yr], Emissions Saving Intensity (ESI) [gCO₂/m².yr], Normalised Investment Cost (NIC) [€/m²], Avoidance Cost (AC) [€/kWh], Simple Payback (SP) [years], Net Present Value (NPV) [€], Profitability Index (PI) [-], Net Present Value Quotient (NPVq) [-], Internal Rate of Return (IRR) [%].

This report provides an overview of these indicators. For more detailed explanation see D6.3 on training material package for using EN-TRACK by FI and investors.

The indicators for EEMs focus on the savings and the return on investments and there are three methods for reporting and benchmarking these indicators in the EN-TRACK platform:

- Simple tracking plots some relevant performance indicator over time and is the first step in measurement-based approaches to energy management.

- Longitudinal benchmarking:
 - Comparison of the building's performance to itself over time. This enables user to determine if performance has deteriorated or improved, to identify opportunities for improvement, to set goals, or to detect unexpectedly high usage.

- Cross-sectional benchmarking:
 - Comparison of the building's performance with a group of similar buildings.

The benchmarking of EEMs in EN-TRACK uses only the cross-sectional approach, comparing various KPIs for single EEM from the same type. Notably, visitor content on the platform is presented with only cross-sectional benchmarking data. Longitudinal benchmarking, on the other hand, is made available to data providers, as it involves non-anonymized data.

The core of the evaluation procedure is the data-driven assessment of the energy savings from the EEMs, which is automated and done through the application of the measurement and verification models for the energy consumption described in D2.3. Depending on the available data granularity of the energy consumption, the hourly or monthly model is used. Once the energy savings are determined, the financial and emissions savings are calculated by using the energy pricing and emissions factors introduced in the system.

EN-TRACK aims to assess the individual effect of each EEM separately and to provide benchmarking for single EEM types. The EEMs are introduced in the system separately but are internally related to renovation projects depending on how close the application dates of the EEM are to each other. D2.3 provides detailed insights on how EN-TRACK's results are produced.

4.1 Energy Use Saving Intensity (EUSI)

The energy use saving intensity (EUSI) is used when you want to compare the energy saving performance of energy efficiency measures in different buildings.

It is one of the key indicators you will see when benchmarking buildings in EN-TRACK

To access the EUSI follow the steps below.

- On the EN-TRACK landing page click on the “Explore” button under the Energy efficiency measures or click on the top click on “Energy Efficiency Measures” on the left side of the top bar as seen in figure 7

Figure 7. EN-TRACK landing page

- This opens the EUSI located under the Energy Saving EEMs benchmarking as seen in figure 8 below.

Figure 8. EUSI indicator page

- Users can toggle between Total Consumption, Electricity, Gas, Heavy Fuel Energy Consumption Diesel and District Heating located on the top of the indicator section. See figure 9.

Figure 9. EUSI indicator page highlighting the toggle modes.

A low EUSI generally represents a building which already has good energy performance, and therefore, implicitly, relatively low potentials for saving energy through EEMs. However, building typologies with higher energy use intensities tend to portray higher EUSI, (For example, a hospital uses significantly more energy than a school).

4.2 Energy Cost Saving Intensity (ECSI)

This indicator is used for comparing the performance of the savings generated by the EEMs in different buildings. This is highly relevant to use if the user is looking into structuring an energy performance contract or similar financing method for a project and would like to compare how the potential projects could compare to other existing projects and buildings around the EU.

To access the ECSI follow the steps below.

- On the EN-TRACK landing page click on the “Explore” button under the Energy efficiency measures or click on the top click on “Energy Efficiency Measures” on the left side of the top bar as seen in figure 7.

- This opens the EUSI located under the Energy Saving EEMs benchmarking as seen in figure 8. To open ECSI click on the Financial Savings icon on the capsule shaped bar as seen in figure 10.

Figure 10. ECSI indicator page

4.3 Energy Emissions Saving Intensity (ESI)

The EESI indicator tells the user how the EEMs are performing in terms of CO₂ reductions. Using EN-TRACK, the user can, through this indicator, get an insight into how they can use energy efficiency in their building portfolios to reach their CO₂ targets while maintaining a profitable investment in the best way for each building typology.

To access the EESI, follow the steps below.

- On the EN-TRACK landing page click on the “Explore” button under the Energy efficiency measures or click on the top click on “Energy Efficiency Measures” on the left side of the top bar as seen in figure 7.
- This opens the EESI located under the Energy Saving EEMs benchmarking as seen in figure 8. To open EESI click on the Emissions Savings icon on the capsule shaped bar as seen in figure 11.

Figure 11. EESI indicator page

4.4 Normalised Investment Cost (NIC) and Avoidance Cost (AC)

NIC tells the user how much the EEM has cost per square metre. This indicator helps in understanding the true earnings per EEM. It also provides an accurate assessment of how an EEM will affect a building, regardless of the size of the building.

Avoidance cost is the measurement of energy and cost savings directly related to certain EEMs. AC provides the total cost per unit of energy saved by an EEM. In other words, avoidance cost is the monetary amount you can avoid spending as a result of the implementation of these EEMs.

To access the NIC and AC, follow the steps below.

- On the EN-TRACK landing page click on the “Explore” button under the Energy efficiency measures or click on the top click on “Energy Efficiency Measures” on the left side of the top bar as seen in figure 7.

- This opens the EUSI located under the Energy Saving EEMs benchmarking as seen in figure 8. To open NIC and AIC click on the Financial Savings icon on the capsule shaped bar as seen in figure 12.

Figure 12. NIC and AIC indicator page

4.5 Internal Rate of Return (IRR), Simple Payback (Years), Net Present Value (NPV) and Profitability Index (PI)

The **Internal Rate of Return (IRR)** is a metric used in financial analysis to estimate the profitability of potential investments. The IRR is the annual rate of growth that an investment is expected to generate. The higher an IRR, the more desirable an investment is to undertake. IRR is uniform for investments of varying types and, as such, can be used to rank multiple prospective investments or projects on a relatively even basis. In general, when comparing investment options with other similar characteristics

Simple Payback: The payback period is the time it takes to recover the cost of an investment or the time an investor needs to reach breakeven. Using this indicator in EN-TRACK allows the user to understand which EEMs suit your current cash flow needs and risk profile best.

NPV is used in capital budgeting and investment planning to analyse the profitability of a projected investment or project. If the NPV of a project or investment is positive, it means that the discounted present value of all future cash flows related to that project or investment will be positive, and therefore attractive. In EN-TRACK, a default discount rate of 5% is assumed for the NPV calculation. The user is allowed to introduce a custom discount rate for specific calculations. **Net Present Value Quotient (NPVq)** is the ratio between the Net Present Value (NPV) and the investment made. It shows what discounted amount is generated against a unit of investment.

The **Profitability Index** also referred to as the benefit-cost ratio is an appraisal technique commonly applied in project finance. It is helpful to FIs because it effectively allows the ranking of different projects in terms of value per investment unit. As with the NPV calculation discussed above, PI calculations require a discount rate to be applied to future cash flows. In EN-TRACK the default discount rate will be set at 5%. The user will be allowed to introduce a custom discount rate for specific calculations.

To access the internal rate of return (IRR), Simple Payback, Net Present Value (NPV), Profitability Index (PI) follow the steps below.

- On the EN-TRACK landing page click on the “Explore” button under the Energy efficiency measures or click on the top click on “Energy Efficiency Measures” on the left side of the top bar as seen in figure 7.

- This opens the EUSI located under the Energy Saving EEMs benchmarking as seen in figure 8. To open ECSI click on the Financial Savings icon on the capsule shaped bar as seen in figure 13.

Energy Efficiency Measures benchmarking

Figure 13. Internal Rate of Return (IRR), Simple Payback (Years), Net Present Value (NPV) Net Present Value Quotient (NPVq), Profitability Index (PI) Indicator Page

4.6 Energy Use Intensity (EUI)

The Energy Use Intensity (EUI) indicator is used to evaluate and assess the energy efficiency performance of a building's design and/or operation. Building EUI is typically expressed as energy consumption per unit area (e.g., energy use per or square meter) and provides a standardized measure of energy efficiency.

- On the EN-TRACK landing page click on the “Compare” button under Buildings or click on the top click on “Building Performance” on the left side of the top bar as seen in figure 14.

Figure 14. EUI indicator page

- This opens the EUI located under the Building Performance benchmarking as seen in figure 15 below.

Figure 15. EUI indicator page

- Users are able to toggle between Electricity, Gas, Heavy Fuel Energy Consumption, Diesel, District Heating and Others located on the top of the indicator section. See figure 16.

Figure 16. ESI indicator page highlighting the toggle modes.

4.7 Energy Cost Intensity (ECI)

The Energy Cost Intensity (ECI) indicator is used to assess and compare the energy costs associated with operating a building relative to its size, expressed as Euro per square meter per year.

- On the EN-TRACK landing page click on the “Compare” button under Buildings or click on the top click on “Building Performance” on the left side of the top bar as seen in figure 14.
- This opens the ESI located under the Building Performance benchmarking as seen in figure 15. To open ECI click on the Cost on the capsule shaped bar as seen in figure 17.

Figure 17. ECI indicator page

4.8 Energy Emissions Intensity (EEI)

Energy Emissions Intensity (EEI) is an indicator used to assess the environmental impact of a building or portfolio of buildings in terms of the level of CO₂ emissions associated with the energy use in the building. It is expressed as gCO₂ per square meter per period of time.

- On the EN-TRACK landing page click on the “Compare” button under Buildings or click on the top click on “Building Performance” on the left side of the top bar as seen in figure 14.
- This opens the ESI located under the Building Performance benchmarking as seen in figure 15. To open EEI click on the Emissions on the capsule shaped bar as seen in figure 18.

Figure 18. EEI indicator page

5 Platform integration developments

As the EN-TRACK platform development is being finalized, the integration with Joule Assets eQuad platform is also progressing. It is expected that the use case scenario for some investors will change once this integration is in place and therefore this document along with any subsequent communication and/or material will be updated accordingly with additional material on eQuad.

The below three use cases are the basis of the integration:

- UC1, Incorporation of data from eQuad to EN-TRACK
- UC2, Exporting benchmarking data from EN-TRACK to eQuad
- UC3, Enabling access from EN-TRACK for financial assessment of new projects with eQuad

Use case 2 will enable financial institutions to benchmark eQuad projects within eQuad using EN-TRACK data, which will add value in determining the viability of a project.

Use case 3 will enable EN-TRACK users to seamlessly transfer their buildings from EN-TRACK to eQuad and turn them into projects for financial assessment and financing processing, adding value in building stock and projects available to investors.

These use cases mainly affect building owners and project developers in terms of operability. They also offer added value to financial institutions although their use of both platforms will not drastically change.

6 Conclusion

Most financial institutions will be familiar with the indicators and methodologies presented in this report. Furthermore, they probably already understand how to use them for EE related matters and also appreciate their value to their organization. For this reason, this document has focussed on providing financial institutions with a comprehensive guide, illustrating how to access, navigate and source various outputs. It also provides hints to enable financial institutions to access and effectively utilize the EN-TRACK platform outputs. The goal is to enable financial institutions to speedily learn how to best utilise the platform to suits their daily operational needs.

This report also serves as a foundational framework for the development of future training materials intended for the EN-TRACK platform. It seeks to demonstrate the methods for accessing, navigating, and sourcing information from the platform, specifically designed to cater to the requirements of financial institutions. These materials will form a robust foundation for the creation of various training formats, including videos, platform wikis, and communication resources.

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Appendix 1: Usability testing survey

Platform Usability Survey

The following survey within the framework of the [EN-TRACK project](#) aims to detect potential improvements and new functionalities to improve the information services for Financial Institutions dealing with Energy Efficiency projects in Buildings.

18 Questions, time to answer: 10 to 15 minutes

IDENTIFICATION

This information will only be used for internal management purposes of the EN-TRACK project.

1. Your name

1/8

10/23/23, 12:14 PM

Mailchimp Survey

2. Your email*

email@example.com

Subscribe me to your newsletter

3. In which country/ies do you operate or does your office cover?*

OPERATIONAL QUESTIONS

Understanding your use of the EN-TRACK platform.

4. Which of the following options are the main reasons for using it?*

Benchmark and compare the energy performance of buildings before and after the installation of energy efficiency measures.

Benchmark and compare the financial performance of energy efficiency projects in buildings.

Track the performance of projects funded by grants or other government spending.

Benchmark your building against other buildings in terms of energy use intensity

Benchmark and compare the performance of specific energy efficiency measures or technologies in terms of energy savings.

Benchmark and compare the performance of specific energy efficiency measures or technologies in terms of return on investment (ROI)

2/8

Analyse trends in the financial performance of investments in energy efficiency measures

Other

5. What are your investment areas?*

Public buildings

Private buildings

Residential buildings

Commercial buildings

Industrial buildings

None of the above

6. Are you currently investing in or have any involvement in Energy Efficiency projects?

*

Yes

No

7. How often do you need financial KPIs in your day-to-day work?*

Daily

Weekly

Monthly

Occasionally

None of the above

LET'S PRACTICE

Please, go to <https://entrack.cimne.com> and try to answer the following practical questions.

8. Exercise 1. Go to the Building Performance tab in the Energy Use Intensity indicator:

8.1. How many buildings are considered in the benchmarking?

5,876

1,003

Other

8.2. Which type of building has the most potential for improvement (the highest average EUI)?

Office

Public

Other

8.3. Apply a filter for an area size of a minimum of 5,000 m² and a maximum of 15,000 m², is your previous answer still valid?

Yes

No

9. Exercise 2. Go to the Energy Efficiency Measures (EEM) tab in the COST tab indicators:

9.1. Which type of EEM has the highest Normalised Investment Cost (Average)?

Building Fabric Measures

HVAC and Hot Water Measures

Renewable Generation Measures

9.2. Which type of EEM has the lowest Avoidance Cost (Average)?

Building Fabric Measures

Lighting Measures

Renewable Generation Measures

10. Exercise 3. Go to the Energy Efficiency Measures (EEM) tab in the FINANCE tab indicators:

10.1. Look at the boxplots of the Internal Rate of Return indicator, which EEM has a higher certainty of return on investment?

Building Fabric Measures

HVAC and Hot Water Measures

Renewable Generation Measures

Give reasons for your answer.

10.2. Look at the boxplots of the Simple Payback indicator, from your point of view, which EEM type has the shortest payback?

Building Fabric Measures

Lighting Measures

- HVAC and Hot Water Measures
- Renewable Generation Measures

GENERAL QUESTIONS

Please answer the following practical questions.

11. How clear and understandable is the information shown on the platform?

*

1 is Not at all

5 is Very

1	2	3	4	5
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12. How useful are the features and functionalities of the platform for your needs?

*

1 is Not at all

5 is Very

1	2	3	4	5
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13. How user-friendly is the platform?*

1 is Not at all

5 is Very

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---

14. "I think I will use the platform to help me with decisions in my job."*

1 is Not at all

5 is Very

1	2	3	4	5
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15. What do you like most about the platform?*

16. What do you like least about the platform?*

17. EN-TRACK platform offers anonymised Buildings and Energy Efficiency projects KPIs for free during the project lifetime, What do you think the maximum annual cost subscription to the platform could be after the project?

*

18. Do you have any suggestions or recommendations to improve the platform? Or is there anything else you would like to share with us about your experience with the platform?

*

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SEND

